

spraying a suspension of 10^8 *Azorhizobium* cells/ml. Control plants were sprayed with sterile distilled water.

Sesbania plants were harvested at 55 DAS. Fresh and dry weight, nodule number, and nodule biomass/plant

were recorded. Nitrogenase activity was measured by the acetylene reduction technique.

Decapitation without inoculation and inoculation without decapitation increased yield parameters (see table). Decapitation followed by inoculation

produced the highest increase. Decapitating young sesbania plants before stem inoculation could maximize N_2 fixation, dry matter production, and N yield. □

Effect of sesbania and azolla on rice grain and straw yields

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We evaluated *Sesbania rostrata*, *S. aculeata*, and *Azolla microphylla* as N sources for rice during 1987-88 dry (Jun-Sep) and wet (Oct-Feb) seasons. The field had moderately drained clay soil (pH 8.2, EC 0.3 dS/m, 288 kg N/ha, 15 kg P/ha, and 526 kg /ha). CO 43 was planted in 1-m² plots. Fresh biomass of *S. rostrata*, *S. aculeata*, and *Azolla microphylla* at 20 t/ha with N content 3.7%, 2.9%, and 2.5% in the dry season and 3.64%, 3.05%, and 2.37% in the wet season, respectively, were incorporated 2 d before planting and allowed to decompose. Prilled

Effect of green manure on rice grain and straw yields. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	Dry season	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season
Control	2.3	2.8	6.2	6.5
Prilled urea				
60 kg N/ha	2.8	3.2	6.4	6.8
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. rostrata</i>	5.7	6.0	14.0	14.1
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. aculeata</i>	4.4	4.7	12.6	12.8
60 kg N/ha + <i>A. microphylla</i>	3.5	4.0	6.8	7.4
100 kg N/ha	3.7	3.9	7.0	7.3
Neem-coated urea				
60 kg N/ha	3.2	3.7	7.0	7.0
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. rostrata</i>	5.9	6.2	14.4	15.1
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. aculeata</i>	5.0	5.1	13.2	14.3
60 kg N/ha + <i>A. microphylla</i>	3.9	4.5	8.3	9.0
100 kg N/ha	3.9	4.3	8.8	8.8
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.4	0.7	0.9	0.3

urea (PU) and neem-coated prilled urea (NCU) were applied at 60 and 100 kg N/ha, in a random block design with three replications. K and P (50 kg/ha) were basally applied.

S. rostrata and *S. aculeata* with 60 kg N/ha significantly increased grain and straw yields (see table). In all treatments, NCU enhanced yields more than did PU alone. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Potential antagonist of rice sheath rot (ShR) pathogen

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We studied the antagonistic potential of some phylloplane fungal and bacterial isolates on the growth of rice pathogens *Pyricularia oryzae* Cavara, *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan, and *Sarocladium oryzae* Sawada.

Phylloplane isolates of bacteria and fungi obtained from leaf samples taken from healthy plants of seven rice varieties are presented in the table. To test interaction with fungal isolates, the

pathogen and the test organism were placed 4 cm apart on potato-dextrose agar medium in petri plates. To test interaction with bacterial isolates, the pathogen was placed at one end of the

plate and allowed to grow for 3 to 4 d, then the test bacterium was streaked 4 cm from the growing edge of the pathogen colony.

Fungal isolate *Bipolaris zeicola* (Stout) Shoem obtained from IR20 at tillering inhibited mycelial growth of

Population of phylloplane microorganisms in different rice varieties. Coimbatore, India.

Rice variety	Colony-forming units ^a (no./g leaf)			
	Tillering phase		Late boot leaf stage	
	Bacteria × 10 ³	Fungi × 10 ²	Bacteria × 10 ³	Fungi × 10 ²
IR20	24.33	11.33	35.67	12.00
IR50	25.41	11.67	35.67	11.67
CO 43	25.33	11.67	36.00	12.00
ASD16	23.33	12.00	35.00	12.33
IR64	24.67	11.67	35.33	12.33
IR70	24.33	11.33	36.00	13.00
Ponni	25.67	12.60	36.33	13.67

^a Mean of 3 replications.